

Spectrophotometric Studies of Palladium(II), Nickel(II), and Copper(II) with 6-Carboxyl-6-Hydroxyl-3,5-Dichloro Azobenzene-4 Sulphonic Acid (CHDCAS)

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The CHDCAS has been newly synthesised and its pK_1 and pK_2 have been determined to be 3.50 and 7.90 respectively by Spectrophotometric method. It forms 1:1 complex with Cu(II) at pH 4.0 (λ_{max} 510 nm.), Pd(II) at pH 1.0 (λ_{max} 550 nm.) and it forms 1:2 complex with Ni(II) at pH 7.5 (λ_{max} 500 nm.). The stability constant (log K) of Cu(II)-CHDCAS chelate and Pd(II)-CHDCAS chelate are found to be 10.31 and 15.51 respectively, whereas, the stepwise stability constant of Ni(II)-CHDCAS chelate are 7.43 (log K_1) and 5.53 (log K_2). Analytical studies of these chelates have also been undertaken.

THIS paper describes a detailed study on the synthesis of CHDCAS and determination of acid dissociation constant, complex formation reaction with Cu(II), Pd(II) and Ni(II) and analytical application in the micro determination of these three ions. Although several reagents are available for the determination of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Pd(II)^{1,2} CHDCAS has been used for the determination of these ions because of high solubility of their chelates in water, high stability of the colour and good sensitivity.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents: Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with silica cuvettes of 1 cm thickness have been used for spectrophotometric measurements. A Beckman model H-2, pH meter has been used for pH measurements.

Cu(II), Ni(II), and Pd(II) perchlorate solutions were used which were prepared from A.R. Grade copper sulphate, nickel sulphate and palladium chloride respectively and were standardised³.

The dye (CHDCAS) was synthesised from 4-amino-3-carboxyl benzene sulphonic acid, which was prepared by the method of Harris and Sweet⁴. The acid was diazotized⁵ and immediately coupled with 2, 4-dichlorophenol in alkaline medium. The product was isolated as its barium salt and converted into sodium salt by treating it with calculated amount of sodium sulphate. The sodium salt was recrystallized from aqueous ethanol and free acid was recrystallized from 50% ethanol. The purity

was checked by potentiometric titration. The product was found to be homogeneous by thin layer chromatography. Ligand solution was prepared in aqueous media.

Sodium perchlorate (E. Merck) solution of suitable strength was used to maintain ionic strength.

Results and Discussion

Acid dissociation constants: The acid dissociation constants of the ligand was determined by using spectrophotometric method⁶ and the dissociation of the ligand may be represented as:

The value of pK_1 and pK_2 have been found to be 3.50 and 7.80 respectively. Calvin and Bjerrum's technique^{7,8}, at an initial ionic strength of 0.04 M has also used to determine the pK values, the value are 3.48 and 7.68 respectively.

The $-SO_3H$ group present might be dissociating at lower pH value and thus not permitting its determination under the present conditions of study. The pK_2 value has been further refined by spectrophotometric method from the relation:

$$pK = pH + \log \frac{A_1 - A'}{A - A_M}$$

Where, A_I and A_M are the absorbances of the ion and the molecule of the ligand and A that of a series of mixtures of ions and molecules. This gave a value of 7.9 for pk_2 .

Characteristics of the complexes : The nature and number of complexes formed were determined. The method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁹ was employed by preparing four series of solutions containing different ratios of ligand to metal as 1 : 0, 4 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 4. The initial solution used to prepare different series of solutions were equimolar ($5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) for the metal and ligand. In each series a number of mixtures were prepared and the pH of these were adjusted to different value between 1.0 to 11.0 and the final volume of the mixture was made 25ml with distilled water of corresponding pH. Absorption spectra of these solution show that the λ_{max} of the complex remains almost constant within the pH range of study (pH 2.0-11.0 for Cu(II) chelate, 5.0-11.0 for Ni(II) chelate, 0.5-11.0 for Pd(II) chelate). It is seen that only one complex is formed in each system. The ligand forms 1 : 1 complex with Cu(II) at pH 4.0 (λ_{max} 510 nm), Pd(II) at pH 1.0 (λ_{max} 550 nm), and it forms 1 : 2 complex with Ni(II) at pH 7.5 (λ_{max} 500 nm).

Composition and stability constant of complexes : The composition of the chelates was studied by Job's method of continuous variation, mole ratio method, slope ratio method and potentiometric titration. The results in Table 1 show that Cu(II) and Pd(II) form 1 : 1 complex, whereas Ni(II) formed 1 : 2 complex with CHDCAS. The stability constant (log K) for Cu(II) and Pd(II) chelates and step-wise stability constants for 1 : 2 Ni(II)-CHDCAS chelate were calculated by Janssen's method with suitable modification¹⁰. The results are recorded in Table 1. The values of log K given in Table 1 show that the stability of these three chelates obeys Irving-Williams¹¹ order.

TABLE—1 COMPOSITION AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF CHELATES OF Cu(II), Ni(II), AND Pd(II) WITH CHDCAS.

System	pH	Wave-length nm.	Ionic strength (M)	Composition M : L	Stability Constant at 25°C. log H=11.39
Cu(II)-CHDCAS	4.0	510	0.1	1 : 1	Log K = 10.31
Ni(II)-CHDCAS	7.5	500	0.1	1 : 2	Log K ₁ = 7.43 Log K ₂ = 5.53
Pd(II)-CHDCAS	1.0	550	0.1	1 : 1	Log K = 15.51

^a M : L = Metal/Ligand

Evaluation of Chromogenic properties and spectrophotometric determination : The colour formation of Cu(II), Ni(II), and Pd(II) chelates is instantaneous. The chelates are stable for more than seven days at room temperature and the maximum colour formation is only attained when the mixture contains greater than four fold excess of reagent with respect to Cu(II), six fold with respect to Ni(II) and five fold with respect to Pd(II).

The use of azodyes as chromatographic spraying reagent is well known¹². The bright and stable colour of these complexes suggested the use of these ligands as spraying reagents for the detection of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Pd(II).

The optimum pH ranges are 4.0-7.0 for Cu(II)-CHDCAS, 7.5-7.8 for Ni(II)-CHDCAS and 0.5-1.0 for Pd(II)-CHDCAS. The various spectral properties including Beer's law and effective spectrophotometric range, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity, relative mean deviation and standard deviation are given in Table 2.

Effect of diverse ions : For studying the effect of diverse ions a difference of $\pm 2\%$ in absorbance value was arbitrarily taken as an interference. The ions which do not interfere at all concentrations are F^- , Br^- , I^- , ClO_4^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , SO_4^{2-} , CrO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , $C_4H_4O_6^{3-}$, $C_6H_5O_3^{3-}$, Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Sn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} . The ions Cr^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Zn^{2+} interfere seriously at all concentrations in the determination of Cu(II). Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Hg^{2+} interfere in the determination of Ni(II) and the ions Pt^{4+} , Rh^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} seriously interfere in the determination of Pd(II).

Spectrophotometric determination of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Pd(II) : To the metal ion solution containing 1.2-5.8 ppm. of Cu(II), add four fold excess of reagent solution and adjust pH of the mixture to 4.0. Allow the mixture to stand for half an hour for equilibrium and then measure the absorbance at 510 nm.

To the metal ion solution (1.1-5.0 ppm. for Ni(II) and 1.2-10.0 ppm. for Pd(II)) add about six fold and five fold excess reagent respectively. Adjust the pH of mixture to 7.5 and 1.0 for Ni(II) and Pd(II) respectively. Allow the mixture to stand for 10 minutes for equilibrium and note the absorbance at 500 and 550 nm for Ni(II) and Pd(II) respectively.

TABLE—2 SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHELATES

System	pH	Wave-length nm.	($\mu g/cm^2$) Sandell's sensitivity	Molar absorptivity	Relative mean deviation percent in	Standard Deviation	Beer's Law (ppm)	Effective range (ppm)
Cu(II)-CHDCAS	4.0	510	0.013	8,840	0.71	0.0036	0.16- 6.30	1.1- 5.8
Ni(II)-CHDCAS	7.5	500	0.010	8,000	0.62	0.0054	0.13- 5.40	0.9- 5.0
Pd(II)-CHDCAS	1.0	550	0.026	7,000	1.21	0.0055	0.30-10.83	1.3-10.3

Structure of Chelates: The anionic nature of the Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) chelates was established by electrophoresis and ion exchange using resin Amberlite IR-45 (OH). The appearance of only one inflection in the potentiometric titration corresponding to the addition of 2 moles of base per mole of ligand indicates the complete neutralization of the sulphonic acid group and carboxylic acid group in a single setp. The phenolic proton of CHDCAS is not titratable under the experimental conditions. In the presence of an equimolar concentration of Cu(II) ions, the phenolic proton gets displaced due to complex formation and becomes titratable, giving a base/ligand ratio of 3. The formation of a 1 : 1 complex was confirmed by potentiometric titrations of the ligand in the presence of Cu(II), at ligand/metal ratios of 2 and 3 also.

M = Ni(II)
Structure II

The liberation of proton during complex formation of Pd(II) with CHDCAS could not be studied by potentiometric method because of high tendency of Pd(II) of getting hydrolysed even at lower pH.

In the case of Ni(II), the formation of 1 : 2 complex (metal : ligand) is confirmed by titrating the mixtures containing 0 : 1, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 mole ratio of Ni(II) and CHDCAS.

Thus, the Cu(II), Pd(II) and Ni(II) chelates can be assigned tentative structure (I) and (II) which are similar to those suggested by earlier workers for analogous systems.¹²⁻¹⁵

M = Cu(II) or Pd(II)
Structure I

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